

JRP16-ET2.2-TELEVIR

Work package 2

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D- JRP16-ET2.2-TELEVIR-WP2

Open-sourced Bioinformatics platform that allows the user-friendly handling of high-throughput sequencing data (second and third generation) for detection and monitoring of viral emerging threats

Background and Motivation

Virus genome sequencing is now a frontline tool for outbreak detection and tracking, being crucial to rapidly characterize circulating viruses and understand their evolutionary trajectories and phenotypic characteristics with relevance for guiding diagnostics, prophylaxis and research [1, 2]. Nonetheless, the implementation of metagenomics virus diagnostics and routine genomic surveillance can be particularly challenging due to the lack of bioinformatics tools/infrastructures and/or expertise to process and interpret next-generation sequencing (NGS) data. In order to start facing this challenge, INSA previously developed INSaFLU (<https://insaflu.insa.pt/>) [3], an open and user-oriented web-based bioinformatics platform for virus routine genome-based surveillance. On behalf of the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP) TELEVIR (<https://onehealthejp.eu/jrp-tele-vir/>) project, and also as a response to the COVID-19 pandemic and, later on, to the multi-country mpox (MPXV) outbreak, **the platform has been improved and adapted to better accommodate the routine genome-based analyses of the novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2), influenza, MPXV and other viruses.** In parallel, targeting one of the main TELEVIR goals of developing a point-of-incidence (poi) toolbox for identification and characterisation of emerging virus threats for humans and/or domestic and wildlife animals, a brand **new module for metagenomics (second- and third-generation sequencing) virus identification was developed.** The achieved INSaFLU-TELEVIR versatility and functionality is expected to supply public health laboratories and researchers with **user-oriented “start-to-end” bioinformatics framework** (Figure 1) **that can potentiate a strengthened and timely metagenomics virus detection and routine genomics surveillance.**

This deliverable describes the main outcomes of TELEVIR Workpackage 2 (WP2), detailing the main activities behind the:

1. **Upgrade of the existing “surveillance-oriented” bioinformatics component**
2. **Development and implementation of a novel metagenomics virus identification module**

All INSaFLU updates were documented at the INSaFLU documentation webpage (<https://insaflu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>) and Github (<https://github.com/INSaFLU/>), and were made available in both the free online platform (<https://insaflu.insa.pt>) and a locally installable version (<https://github.com/INSaFLU/docker>), with users, TELEVIR partners and other stakeholders (e.g., ECDC) being notified of all novel features throughout the project. Of note, the early development and publicly distribution of a locally installable version of the platform (<https://github.com/INSaFLU/docker>) at the beginning of the project (and continuous maintenance) was particularly relevant towards the ultimate deployment of a portable bioinformatics toolbox that can also fit the needs for field studies, in strong linkage with the WP3 activities (“Development of a wet-lab protocol for point-of-incidence (poi) MinION sequencing”). Both wet- and dry-lab achievements can be combined to support both human and veterinary clinical practice and disease outbreak investigations.

Figure 1. Simplified illustration of the main modules and outputs of INSaFLU-TELEVIR (<https://insaflu.insa.pt>) bioinformatics suite. All INSaFLU functionality is documented at INSaFLU documentation/tutorial webpage (<https://insaflu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>) and Github (<https://github.com/INSaFLU/>).

Main activities and achievements

The main activities and achievements regarding the two main components of the INSaFLU platform, “routine genomic surveillance” and “metagenomics virus detection”, are summarized below.

1. Upgrade the existing “surveillance-oriented” bioinformatics component

(from NGS reads to quality control, mutations detection, consensus generation, virus classification, alignments, “genotype-phenotype” screening, phylogenetics, integrative phylogeographical and temporal analysis etc)

- **Development, optimization and implementation of an automated pipeline for Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) data analysis**, from raw reads to quality analysis, reference-based generation/curation of consensus sequences, mutation annotation, gene/protein/genome alignments, phylogenetic tree, metadata visualization, etc (complementing the existing pipeline for Illumina / Ion Torrent technologies). By automatically detecting the sequencing technologies and subsequently allocating a technology-specific pipeline, the platform allows flexible data analysis and sequence comparison regardless of the technology used. This flexibility is particularly useful, for instance, in the context of routine genomic epidemiology systems with centralized data analysis, but decentralized sequencing with distinct technologies;
- **Enrichment of the default Reference database** with the publicly available reference genome sequence for SARS-CoV-2, MPXV and influenza;
- **Enrichment of the classification databases with genetic markers for Human Betacoronaviruses and MPXV** (complementing the existing database for rapid identification and classification of all influenza type and sub-type identification), **and extension of this classification module to ONT data**;
- **Extension of the software parameterization (“Settings”)** features, allowing users to configure key parameters for reads quality analysis, mapping and consensus generation, while **making settings parameterization more flexible and tailored to handle distinct sequencing technologies (Illumina, IonTorrent and ONT) and distinct NGS data from multiple viruses**.
- **Integration of novel features for automated refinement/curation of consensus sequences**, e.g., automatic introduction of undefined nucleotides (“N”) in low coverage regions, regions (or nucleotide sites) selected to be masked by the user (e.g., error-prone regions) or sites where the mutation frequency is below the user-defined cut-off;
- **Integration of automatic SARS-CoV-2 Pango lineage** (<https://pangolin.cog-uk.io/>) assignment using Pangolin (<https://github.com/cov-lineages/pangolin>), as described by Rambaut and colleagues [4]. To better fit this dynamic lineage nomenclature, whenever new software/database versions are released, a button “Update Pango lineage” is automatically

made available, so that users can re-assign all samples using the latest software/database versions.

- **Integration of direct links to Nextclade (<https://clades.nextstrain.org/>) for flexible SARS-CoV-2, seasonal influenza and MPXV consensus sequences analysis.** This feature allows INSaFLU consensus sequences to be easily subjected to quality screening, clade classification, mutation exploration and other analyses available at the Nextclade framework.
- **Development and incorporation into the INSaFLU platform of a bioinformatics tool (“algn2pheno”) for rapid screening of genetic features potentially linked to specific phenotypes** (<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/algn2pheno>; <https://pypi.org/project/algn2pheno/>). This tool takes as input an amino acid or nucleotide / alignment (as generated by the existing INSaFLU pipeline), and detects mutations in each of the sequences. It then rapidly screens these mutations against a database of known genotype-phenotype associations (such as, amino acid site changes already linked to: antiviral resistance, resistance to neutralizing antibodies, enhanced affinity to host-receptors antibodies or enhanced transmissibility), and generates a user-friendly overview of “phenotypes” predicted for each sequence. The pilot integration of the algn2pheno tool into the INSaFLU platform targeted the automated generation of user-friendly reports on a repertoire of “relevant” SARS-CoV-2 Spike mutations. This functionality automatically screens SARS-CoV-2 Spike amino acid alignments in each SARS-CoV-2 project against two default “genotype-phenotype” databases: the COG-UK Antigenic mutations (<https://sars2.cvr.gla.ac.uk/cog-uk/>) and the Pokay Database (<https://github.com/nodrogluap/pokay/tree/master/data>). **Align2pheno then reports the full repertoire of Spike amino acid changes found in each sequence, flagging the presence of mutations of interest (and their potential impact on phenotype) included in those databases.** Apart from its implementation in the bioinformatics platform, the standalone version of the algn2pheno tool already facilitated the identification and selection of viruses with potentially distinct phenotypic (e.g. antigenic) profiles for downstream comparative assays in the COVRIN (<https://onehealthejp.eu/jip-covrin/>) project: (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6784043>), showing the advantage of building bridges between ongoing One Health EJP activities to enhance the identification of drivers of the emergence and spread of new pathogen threats and the generation of supportive data for risk assessment. This module is intended to be extended to additional viruses and genotype-phenotype database formats (such as, those relying in multiple reference sequences, e.g., influenza). In this regard, a scoping review and construction of a comprehensive database of mutations with effect on phenotype for influenza has been already prototyped (<https://zenodo.org/record/7455415#.Y5-QDXbP02w>). Additionally, we have investigated the feasibility of inferring biochemical and immunological properties of viruses detected at POI. In work aligned with JIP COVRIN, we have explored SARS-CoV-2 antigenic variation and its genetic determinants, using antigenic cartography. Antigenic distances between key SARS-CoV-2 variants have been measured using both rabbit sera, and human vaccine sera for comparison with genetic data. We have also highlighted differences between species' responses, with implications for cross-species

transmission, and between booster doses in humans, providing evidence to support public health advice [5].

- **Inclusion of novel interactive and dynamic “expand-and-collapse” panels for enhanced report** of: i) all detected mutations (including detailed information about genome position, nucleotide change, coverage evidence, frequency, impact at protein level, etc.); ii) the mean depth of coverage and horizontal coverage per locus for all samples using intuitive color-coded buttons; iii) “aln2pheno” mutations potentially linked to known phenotypes;
- **Upgrade of the existing features for phylogenetic trees visualization** using PhyloCanvas features (<https://github.com/phylocanvas>) to easily colour tree nodes and to display coloured metadata blocks next to the phylogenetic trees nodes, thus facilitating integration of relevant epidemiological and/or clinical data and pathogen genomic data.
- **Integration of Nextstrain (<https://nextstrain.org/>) through a new module “Datasets” for advanced visualization and exploration of phylogenetic and genomic data together with geographic and temporal data** (or any other epidemiologically relevant metadata variable). INSaFLU allows running virus-specific Nextstrain builds (seasonal Influenza, SARS-CoV-2 and Monkeypox) as well as a “generic” build that can be used for other viruses, while providing flexibility to perform temporal and phylogeographical analysis involving consensus sequences generated in the platform as well as external sequences (e.g., sequences retrieved from GenBank or GISAID). In interaction with the One Health EJP project “BeOne: Building Integrative Tools for One Health Surveillance” (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-beone/>), work is ongoing to incorporate other tools, namely ReporTree (<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree>), which is a flexible pipeline that facilitates the detection of pathogen genetic clusters and their linkage with surveillance (clinical /epidemiological) metadata;
- **Improvement of the local installation mode and data uploading**, by allowing, e.g., uploading read data and metadata directly from command line. Tools to automate the concatenation of multiple output files from ONT runs files in Windows operating system were also released;
- **Release of a pilot command line version of the surveillance-component of INSaFLU** (using the snakemake workflow manager)
- **Continuous optimization of the user interface** so that it can provide final graphical outputs that can be easily interpreted by a broad audience, not only bioinformaticians, but also other scientists (e.g., virologists, epidemiologists) or even decision makers with little computational background. This “front-end” work was complemented with a continuous optimization of the “back-end” computational capacities and queue management in the online tool (<https://insaflu.insa.pt/>).

2. Development and implementation of a novel metagenomics virus identification module

(from NGS reads to quality control and metagenomics virus identification)

One of the main goals of the TELEVIR WP2 was also to **upgrade the platform for automatic metagenomics virus identification in order to support both human and veterinary clinical practice and disease outbreak investigations**. After reviewing the current state-of-the-art of the field of bioinformatics pipelines for metagenomics virus diagnostics, a **modular pipeline was developed, incorporating the key steps of metagenomics taxonomic classification (Figure 2)**, namely: read quality control, viral enrichment / host depletion, draft assembly, reads/contigs taxonomic classification, confirmatory reference-based remapping and reporting (detailed below).

Figure 2. Simplified illustration of the main steps of the modular INSaFLU-TELEVIR bioinformatics pipeline for metagenomics virus diagnostics.

The functionalities of the main steps of the TELEVIR component can be summarized as follows:

- **Read quality analysis and improvement:** This step takes the input single- or paired-end reads (fastq.gz format; ONT or Illumina) and produces quality processed reads, as well as quality control reports for each file, before and after this step. This module overlaps the two components (virus detection and surveillance) of the platform.
- **Viral Enrichment:** This step retains potential viral reads based on a rapid and permissive classification of the reads against a viral sequence database. This step is performed directly over raw reads (if QC was turned OFF) or quality processed reads (if QC was turned ON).
- **Host depletion:** This step removes potential host reads based on reference-based mapping against host genome sequence(s). Mapped reads are treated as potential host reads and removed. This step will act on virus enriched sequences, unless the Viral enrichment step was turned OFF, in which case host depletion will be directly performed over raw reads (if QC was turned OFF) or quality processed reads (if QC was turned ON).
- **De novo assembly:** This step performs *de novo* assembly using reads retained after the "Viral enrichment" and/or "Host depletion" steps. If the latter steps were turned OFF, assembly will be directly performed using raw reads (if QC was turned OFF) or quality processed reads (if QC was turned ON).
- **Identification of viral sequences:** This step screens reads and contigs against viral sequence databases, generating intermediate read and/or contig classification reports with a list of viral hits (TAXID and representative accession numbers) potentially present in the sample.
- **Selection of viral TAXID and representative genome sequences for confirmatory analysis:** In this step, the previously identified viral hits (TAXID) are selected for confirmatory mapping against reference viral genome(s) present in the available databases. Viral TAXIDs are selected, up to a maximum number of hits, as follows: 1^o - Viral hits corresponding to phages are removed from classification report; 2^o - TAXIDs present in both intermediate classification reports (reads and contigs) are selected; 3^o - additional TAXIDs are selected across the read classification report (by number of hits, in decreasing order) and contigs classification report (by number of hits and total length of matching sequences, from top-down) until reaching the defined maximum number of hits to be selected (this number is to be user-defined).
- **Remapping of the viral sequences against selected reference genomes.** This step maps reads and/or contigs against representative genome sequences of the selected viral TAXIDs collected in the previous step. Reads are also mapped against the set of contigs classified for each TAXID. Of note, TAXIDs that were not automatically selected for this confirmatory re-mapping step (but that were present in the intermediate reads and/or contigs classification reports) can still be user-selected for mapping at any time.
- **Reporting.** The workflow culminates in user-oriented reports (Figure 3) with a list of the most-likely suspected viruses, each accompanied by several robust and diagnostic-oriented metrics, statistics and visualizations, provided as (interactive) tables (intermediate and final reports),

graphs (e.g., coverage plots, Integrative Genomics Viewer visualization, Assembly to reference dotplots) and multiple downloadable output files (e.g., list of the software parameters, reads/contigs classification reports, mapped reads/contigs identified per each virus; reference sequences, etc.).

Figure 3. Reporting dashboard of the INSaFLU-TELEVIR bioinformatics module for metagenomics virus detection.

During development, in order to finely explore the best approaches to be implemented in the TELEVIR toolbox, **we benchmarked several workflows**. For this, we tested combinations of modules that comprise the overall virus identification pipeline: Viral Enrichment, Assembly and Classification (of reads and contigs). Specifically, we tested software (such as [Centrifuge](#), [Diamond](#), [Kaiju](#), [Kraken2](#), [KrakenUniq](#), [BLAST](#)) and databases (such as [NCBI](#), [RVDB](#), [UniProt](#), [Virosaurus](#)) commonly used in virological diagnostic laboratories for clinical metagenomics, as well as some more recent but promising alternative classifiers ([deSAMBA](#), [FastViromeExplorer](#), [Clark](#)). As input, we used reads datasets (retrieved from literature or provided by TELEVIR partners) that have been well characterized by RT-PCR, which allowed us to calibrate our experiments. For the final evaluation, we relied on a subset of the reporting statistics, namely coverage and the proportion of mapped reads, but we also looked at the true positive rate (the proportion of viral hits corresponding to the expected virus) and a measure of evidence completeness (reads and/or contigs) (Figure 4). We ran 156 combinations (i.e., different

software, reference databases and/or parameters) on 22 ONT samples (a total of 3432 runs) experiments. For each step along the TELEVIR pipeline (Figure 4A), the benchmark revealed strong candidates for the integration in the final ONT workflow, often culminating in the identification of a single good performant software: Viral Enrichment obtained better results with the software Centrifuge; at the Assembly and contig classification steps, the Raven and Minimap2 software obtained better results, respectively. Finally, for the read classification step, we took into consideration the need for independent validation and decided to retain multiple software. We chose the four best combinations: KrakenUnig, FastViromeExplorer, Centrifuge and Kaiju (in order of performance). For Illumina data, our choice of the workflow was guided by an early small-scale benchmark following the same rationale and strategy. Further benchmarking studies (in particular, for Illumina data) are ongoing in order to extend/refine the virus metagenomics detection module. Of note, the choice of workflows implemented in the first release has also benefited from the multiple testing performed on behalf of TELEVIR WP3 (development of a wet-lab protocol for POI virus detection) and WP4 (field studies) activities.

Figure 4. Simplified illustration of the benchmark of the ONT virus identification pipeline module components. **a.** Tree representation of module combinations. From top to bottom, sections represent pipeline steps as followed at runtime: **1.** Quality Control, **2.** Viral Enrichment, **3.** Assembly, **4.** Contig classification, **5.** Read Classification. Nodes represent software, parameters or databases compared. Colour gradient corresponds to the product of four assessment statistics: mapped reads proportion, horizontal coverage, true positive rate and completeness. Statistics were standardized by their respective maxima. **b.** Benchmark subtree of the right-most node, from contig classification down. Final ONT workflow selection stems from this tree. **c.** Table of individual statistics for the 13 nodes of the subtree represented in b., standardized by column. For all panels, darker colours = lower values, lighter colours = higher values.

In summary, as expected, there is no “one-size-fits-all” approach that can detect all viruses, but a set of “well-performing” workflows that together can potentiate the detection of clinical relevant viruses. To accommodate this observation, **the implemented solution was precisely designed to have this flexibility by allowing users to simultaneously run those complex workflows (covering the optimized combination of classification algorithms, databases, etc.) in a user-friendly manner.** In parallel, work was carried out to design, develop and implement user-friendly visual solutions for output reporting, keeping the same rationale and design of the “routine genomics surveillance” component (Figure 3). In fact, independent of the workflow(s) that are ultimately included into the platform as defaults, **each run culminates in user-oriented reports with a list of the most-likely suspected viruses, each accompanied by several robust and diagnostic-oriented metrics. This emphasis on the usefulness and accessibility of end-user reports serves to strengthen output interpretation and decision-making on the part of users.** The new diagnosis-oriented “virus detection” module is publicly distributed within the INSaFLU-TELEVIR platform (both in the online tool and locally installable versions), coupled with its inter-connectivity with the existing “surveillance-oriented” component for an enhanced detection and monitoring of viral pathogens.

Divuligation, Impact and Future perspectives

Divuligation

The National Institute of Health (INSA) Doutor Ricardo Jorge, Portugal, has presented the INSaFLU-TELEVIR open web-based bioinformatics suite for virus genome-based surveillance on behalf of several international initiatives and networks, e.g., ECDC COVID-19 Laboratory Networks Influenza, WHO Europe Laboratory Workshop. INSA also maintains several cooperative actions at national and international levels to enhance the capacity building of other national and international laboratories (e.g., National Institute of Health from Guinea-Bissau) in pathogen genome-based surveillance. In this context, the INSaFLU-TELEVIR platform was presented to/in:

- **broad audiences on behalf of:**
 - ECDC COVID-19 Laboratory Networks Influenza (20 May 2020)
 - WHO Europe Laboratory Workshop (1 June 2020).
 - ISIRV-WHO Virtual Conference, COVID-19, Influenza and RSV: Surveillance-Informed Prevention and Treatment, , ARPHA Conference, 2021 (19-21 October 2021)
 - European Society for Clinical Virology (ESCV), 24th Annual Conference, Manchester, UK (9 Sep, 2022)
 - European Society of Clinical Microbiology and Inf Diseases, Webinar (20 Sep, 2022)
 - Mini symposium on Bioinformatics resources, tools and Research (BV-BRC and J. Craig Venter Institute) (15 Sep 2022)

- PROMISE RSV Laboratory Network (RSV-LabNet) (13 Dec 2022)
- MediLabSecure Webinar “Introduction to Metagenomics technologies” (14 Dec 2022)
- **specific countries/reference laboratories (including training sessions):**
 - National Institute of Health from Guinea-Bissau (INASA), Guinea-Bissau (27 August 2021)
 - Norwegian Veterinary Institute (Norway), Norway (19 April 2021)
 - WITS-VIDA, South Africa (24 March 2022)
 - NHS-UK, Scotland, UK (27 September 2022)
 - Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária (INIAV), Portugal (November 2022)
 - Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria (INIA), Spain (7-18 November 2022), in cooperation with the EJP JIP06-COVID19-COVRIN project (Short-term mission)
 - Multiple countries, on behalf of the ongoing ECDC programme to “Support to Microbiology-related Activities and Capacity Building Focusing on Covid-19 and Influenza in the EU/EEA, the Western Balkans and Turkey. Laboratory Support, Training, and Standardisation”.

Impact

On behalf of the TELEVIR project, and also as a response to COVID-19 pandemic and, later on, the multi-country MPXV outbreak, the previously existing INSaFLU (<https://insaflu.insa.pt/>) platform has been improved and adapted to better accommodate the routine genome-based analyses of SARS-CoV-2, influenza, MPXV and other viruses. As a result, the INSAFLU-TELEVIR bioinformatics framework has already been crucial for genomics surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 (<https://insaflu.insa.pt/covid19/>; more than 44000 sequences analysed, as of December 2022), influenza (more than 600 sequences in 2020-2022), and, more recently, MPXV (around 500 samples in 2022) in Portugal. The achieved INSaFLU-TELEVIR versatility and functionality has captured the attention of the scientific community (leading to the considerably increase in the number of accounts created) and several stakeholders, such as ECDC (suggested tool for WGS analysis <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/novel-coronavirus/laboratory-support>). In parallel, multiple national and international activities were conducted (or are being planned) to support the capacity building of other countries/laboratories in metagenomics virus detection and routine genomic surveillance through specific training in the INSaFLU-TELEVIR (see details below).

Future perspectives

Future developments

In a near future, INSaFLU-TELEVIR is expected to be updated to:

- Improve modularity of the surveillance-oriented INSaFLU component, namely by allowing the user to choose alternative methods in different steps of the pipeline (as already implemented for the TELEVIR virus detection module).
- Produce surveillance-oriented reports about pathogen genetic clusters/lineages and their characterization in terms of geotemporal spread or linkage to surveillance (clinical/epidemiological) metadata through the incorporation of ReporTree (<https://github.com/insapathogenomics/ReporTree>).
- Extend the ability to rapidly report potential genotype-phenotype associations, currently implemented only for SARS-CoV-2, to other viruses, by shaping/changing the existing bioinformatics strategy according to the complexity of the database and to accommodate the “segmentation nature” of the virus (e.g., influenza).
- Expand the Nextstrain phylogeographic and temporal analysis, as well as the automation of viral genotyping, to include other clinically relevant viruses, such as the respiratory syncytial virus (RSV).
- Synchronize local and web instances of the platform, allowing an easier integration and sharing of data, so that results of local analysis (“offline”) can be “communicated” to a centralized repository with web access.
- Facilitate data flow and sharing with external resources (GISAID, NCBI, ENA, etc.).

Training

INSA maintains several cooperative actions at national and international levels to enhance the capacity building of other laboratories in pathogen detection and genome-based surveillance, providing specific training in the INSaFLU-TELEVIR platform. For instance, INSA is participating in a 4-year programme launched by ECDC to “Support Microbiology-related Activities and Capacity Building Focusing on Covid-19 and Influenza in the EU/EEA, the Western Balkans and Turkey” (AURORAE project). INSA has also recently established a collaboration with the EU funded MediLabSecure project (<https://www.medilabsecure.com/project.html>) to improve the surveillance and monitoring of emerging zoonotic diseases of viral origin in the Mediterranean, Black Sea and Sahel regions. Several INSaFLU-TELEVIR training sessions to the beneficiary non-EU countries are already planned for the next year (2023). In addition, on behalf of our strict collaboration with countries of Portuguese official language, namely African countries, INSaFLU training was, for instance, recently provided to the National Institute of Health from Guinea-Bissau.

In summary, several INSaFLU training initiatives are planned to strengthen the capacity for genomic epidemiology and public health bioinformatics of key stakeholders, namely laboratories conducting surveillance of emerging viral threats.

Conclusions

The early detection, characterization and surveillance of viruses is an urgent need at a global level in the light of the continuous emergence of viral threats, as recently observed in SARS-CoV-2 and MPXV epidemics. In this context, the TELEVIR consortium worked to establish a POI toolbox, including a wet-lab protocol for metagenomics virus detection using ONT sequencing (WP3), and an open and user-oriented “start-to-end” bioinformatics framework for metagenomics virus detection and routine genomic surveillance (WP2). This deliverable summarized the main activities of WP2, leading to: 1) the improvement and adaptation of the “surveillance oriented” INSaFLU-TELEVIR platform to handle sequence data (ONT, Illumina and Ion Torrent) of “any” virus (from reads to quality control, mutations detection, consensus generation, classification, alignments, “genotype-phenotype” screening, phylogenetics, integrative phylogeographical and temporal analysis, etc.), and 2) the development, benchmarking and implementation of a novel pathogen detection module, from reads and quality control to the identification of both RNA and DNA viruses. Although it was challenging to develop this work in the context of a pandemic and a research field in continuous technological evolution (microbial genomics and metagenomics), the final platform functionalities also benefitted from the real-time software and data sharing at international level, leading to the integration of cutting-edge and state-of-the art bioinformatics features and resources. Indeed, the achieved INSaFLU-TELEVIR versatility and functionality has captured the attention of the scientific community, leading to the considerable increase in the number of users, and to the engagement of the INSaFLU-TELEVIR team in multiple national and international activities (conferences, training programmes, networks and projects) to strengthen the capacity for genomic epidemiology and public health bioinformatics of key stakeholders, namely laboratories/countries conducting surveillance of emerging viral threats. INSaFLU-TELEVIR is a free web-based, and locally installable, platform available at (<https://insaflu.insa.pt/>).

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